

The impact of COVID-19 on the quality of education of the Information Management Master

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the way of enrollment, teaching and examination in higher education. In order to be able to provide education, universities had to adapt by digitally transforming the entire university environment. The impact of the pandemic on the quality of education for IT related Master of Science programs at universities worldwide has been analyzed. The dynamic of the educational IT Governance changed to be able to continue delivering education in accordance with the quality standards. The process of education at a University has been thoroughly analyzed with help of an activity diagram in order to identify potential risks that the digital transformation bears. A risk assessment has been made in order to mitigate these risks and to provide pointers to prolong the future of digital education. This analysis aims to guide the digital transformation of Universities by analyzing the pre-Covid and post-Covid era.

Keywords

COVID-19, Information Management, Education quality, Master, Education.

INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 has accelerated the digital transformation of countries worldwide. In particular, the educational sector had to change drastically in order to be able to provide their services whilst preserving the quality of education. The, normally, traditional educational sector has been impacted severely by the virus. Distance measures ruled out the possibility of hosting lectures with hundreds of students in the same room. The sudden need for digitization of education raises the question of the quality of education. Will online education be able to preserve the quality of the education and be as good as, or even better as, offline education?

Considering the time and resources available, this research is set out to analyze the pre-COVID-19 situation as well as the post-COVID-19 situation of IT related Masters at the University of Nowhere in order to analyze the preservation of the quality of education and to identify improvements for the future. The research has been scoped to IT related Masters since these Masters are representative for the majority of the Masters that are future resistant and in the area of Economics and Management. IT related Masters include practical programming labs, theoretical lectures and possible internships. This diversity of offerings makes it ideal for analysis.

The results of this research aim to extend the understanding of online education and its effect. Furthermore, the results aim to improve the process of online education of Universities in order to better prepare students for the future.

RESEARCH

Objective

The objective of this research is to investigate to what extent the quality of education of the Master programs at universities is influenced by the form of education, physical or virtual.

This research is of high importance since the sudden need for Universities and students to follow virtual education due to the government enforced measures as a result of COVID-19. Universities had to undergo major changes in all areas in a matter of months, changes which normally take years. The small-time window, in which the digital transformation had to take place, has presumably taken its toll on the quality of education of all the different programs. The small window has forced the University to pick external vendors and it has raised a lot of questions for example concerning the

GDPR of the students. Furthermore, the lack of time has forced the University to compromise, leaving out possibilities of standardization and integration. This research aims to analyze the current post-COVID-19 process in order to provide recommendations and improvements for the future, to preserve the quality of education of the Master's program Information Management.

Approach

In this research, data provided by universities will be used. This means that there will be looked at what types of processes are being used in the case of digital learning. There will be a specific focus on the data analysis of the IT department of universities. Furthermore, theoretical knowledge will be retrieved from academic papers related to the impact of COVID-19 on the digital transformation in education specifically.

For this study, the convenience sampling method will be used as this is the easiest and fastest way of sampling. Furthermore, the focus will be on MSc students as they would be willing to help us out as they are all enrolled in this course. Regarding the data collection method, an online survey will be conducted as this is an accurate way to gather data, and it is accessible to anyone. Furthermore, it allows for data to be captured immediately. At last, regression analysis will be used to treat data.

EDUCATION AND CAREER

For this research the level of analysis will be masters at universities. The broad subject has been chosen with regards to the ability to make generalized statements. The main focus, when it comes to masters, will be in the direction of Information Management. Inside the sector of Information management masters, there are four main actors. In the form of students, teachers, the university and the systems they use.

The online delivery of higher education courses and programs has continued to expand across academic disciplines at universities (L.D. Mitchell et al, 2014). Therefore, the place for "offline education", in order of for example the lectures being given in lecture rooms, or assignments and being given out on paper in class, has been transitioning away in the pre-Covid-19 era. Where at the start of this decade classes were almost exclusively given offline and literature was handout on paper. Right before the pandemic, literature was always accessed via links that were shared inside a system by the professor and courses were being accessible online through either recording or just online classes. However, in the pre-Covid era universities were always reluctant to fully accept or engage in the transition to a fully

online environment.

Therefore, the biggest impact that Covid-19 had on the aforementioned actors was still the transition from mostly offline to exclusively online education. This transition impacted every actor differently. For students, we'll be looking at the effects that the transition had on the well-being of students, with regard to both how they have felt and how they have done academically. Teachers had to adapt to a new way of teaching overnight, the effects this had will also be analyzed. And the newfound ways universities applied in order to keep the quality of their education and diploma of high standards.

In order to analyze the well-being of the students, and be able to make a generalizable statement, data will be collected via a survey. Data will be collected on information management students that follow their master in the Netherlands, so for example both Tilburg university and Erasmus University students. The students that are asked to participate have to be studying during the pandemic. So, students that were either finished, in progress or starting during the pandemic. To complement our analyses, mostly literature will be used.

ANALYSIS

IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

IT governance is an instrument for controlling and managing IT resources such as infrastructure technologies and people in any type of organisation, including universities (Bajgoric 2014; De Haes and Van Grembergen 2009; Hicks et al. 2012).

According to the paper of I.Bianchi, R.Sousa (2016), higher education institutions require a variety of information technologies such as software, a university system, cloud applications, wireless networking and e-learning platforms. Accordingly, these information technologies support teaching, learning and researching activities (Coen and Kelly 2007).

In fact, universities in many countries have increasingly recognized the importance of ITG (Jairak et al. 2015). However, despite the recognition of the relevance of ITG by university executives, the level of adoption of IT governance mechanisms is low (Yanosky and Caruso 2008). Bianchi, I., Sousa, R., Pereira, R. & Hillegersberg, J. (2017) came to the conclusion that in IT Governance, process mechanisms are the most relevant for universities, while relational mechanisms are the most effective and easy to implement. Despite the recognition by various stakeholders of the importance of IT Governance

and the alignment between business and IT, the education sector is still largely a Business Monarchy when it comes to IT activities.

Therefore, in order to measure the evolution of the IT function in the education sector, the Strategic Grid framework will be used.

Figure 1 - The strategic grid framework (based on Nolan & McFarlan, 2005)

Before COVID, IT applications were a support. Indeed, they improved business and management performances, but were not critical for them.

The COVID pandemic has completely changed the education environment. Universities were required to opt for digital education solutions. As a result, IT applications evolved from being a support to be critical to sustaining current activities (Factory).

Even if the IT governance of universities and higher education institutions were similar before 2020, universities will be chosen as a model for ease of explanation.

First of all, it is known that universities were very centralized. According to studies, the business strategy was cost focused, the business governance was centralized, the size of the organization was small, the information intensity was low and most importantly the environment was very stable. (W. Van Grembergen, S.De Haes, E.Guldentops, 2004).

It was therefore a committee of senior business executives who make decisions in terms of IT principles (How IT is used in the business), IT architecture (Technical choice to guide the organization in satisfying business needs), IT infrastructure strategies (Strategies for the base foundation of budgeted-for-IT capability) and IT investment and prioritization (Decision about how much and where to invest in IT).

Archetype	IT Activities (Input/Decision)	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy											
IT Monarchy											
Feudal	*			*		*		*		*	
Federal											
IT Duopoly											
Anarchy											

Figure 2 – Governance design matrix before COVID

Inputs are considered as federal because it is the most common and it is not very important in our research.

Now that an overview of the IT Governance is

established in the education sector before COVID, the two eras can be compared. In the case of Tilburg Universities, it was decided to go completely online in mid-March. To do so, they had to buy new equipment, new licenses (Zoom, Proctorio...), as well as to train teachers in these new technologies, check the GDPR condition. In order to put all these new measures in place quickly and in the best possible way, governance must also evolve. IT jobs must become more important.

Indeed, clarifying the role of information technology (IT Principle) in companies and specifying companies' needs in terms of IT applications purchased or developed in-house (Business Application needs) should become a decision to be taken by the Business and IT representatives (IT Duopoly). In addition, defining integration and standardization (IT Architecture) and determining shared and enabling services (IT Infrastructure Strategies) should be managed by IT executives (IT monarchy). However, the last word, which is to choose the initiatives to be financed and the amounts to be spent (IT Investment), should remain with the business executives (Business Monarchy).

Archetype	IT Activities (Input/Decision)	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
		Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy											
IT Monarchy											
Feudal	*			*		*		*		*	
Federal											
IT Duopoly											
Anarchy											

Figure 3 – How Governance Design Matrix should be now

The COVID pandemic have accelerated the evolution of education and thus its governance. Classrooms and all this online system is likely to continue, and keeping this governance matrix in place will help to remain competitive and provide students with the best possible education.

Business Process Integration

Due to regulation given by the government, to limit the spreading of the covid-19 virus, all universities in the Netherlands were closed. This meant that the universities had to change a lot of their core process, if these universities did not want their students to have study delay. Due to these regulations all Universities in the Netherlands were forced into a transition from the classical “offline” way of teaching, to the, perhaps more modern, online teaching.

The definition of Business program integration within the course is given as follows:

“the techniques and mechanisms for managing the movement of data, and the invocation of processes in the correct and proper order to support the management and execution of common processes that exist in and between applications”.

(Linthicum04)

For the integrated business process a fictive course given at an average university that will entail aspects of most courses is used. The changes within the students' journey through a course, ergo the business process, before and after the covid-19 pandemic will be analyzed. The challenges that came with this transition for universities, students and professors as well as the adaption of new technologies by the latter will be analyzed. Next to that the advantages and disadvantages of online education are being analyzed. An advantage, for example, for taking online courses is the increased engagement for students in quantitative reasoning when taking a course. A disadvantage was, for example, the lack of student-professor interactions and discussions between students. (A.D. Dumford and A.L. Miller, 2018).

To be able to analyze the differences between the pre and post Covid era, an activity diagram is used in which assumptions are being made in the way a typical student experiences a course, what input the teachers has, and the way the system interacts between all actors. The diagram shows mostly that Covid-19 has changed the way the lectures are given and exams are taken. And it has given the System a more prominent role in the interaction between teachers and students, due to both the lectures and the exams transitioning from an offline to an online environment.

Since the beginning of the lockdown, schools, colleges, and universities around the world have shifted their classes to video conferencing platforms like Zoom and Google Meet (R. De, N. Pandeyb, A. Pal, 2020)

When comparing both diagrams, this also seems to be the case. The initial process; signing up for a course, has stayed the same. The first differences between both diagrams occur when the teacher and the system interact with each other, this is when the lectures start. In the pre-covid era a classroom had to be reserved for a course so the teacher could give lectures. In this current covid era, lectures are given online, so a teacher has to use a certain type of software that displays themselves good enough to be able to give a lecture. Exams also shifted from an offline to an online environment, which led to a more complex system, seeing that even more software had to be added to make sure the quality of the course was being maintained. The process after the exam is taken by a student is virtually the same, seeing that in both diagrams the teacher had to grade the work provided by the student and the student had to pass the test or resit in order to complete the course and receive the required credits.

When looking further into the advantages and disadvantages the transition from online to offline

education has brought. For example the fact that carbon emission is significantly reduced, due to the lack of student transportation (M. Versteijlen et al. 2017). Not having to go to a certain place, like a university, implies that access to lectures has been improved, because they are not dependent on for example a train being on time to attend a lecture. Disadvantages are that both students and teachers have to adapt to a new environment without having a lot of transitioning time. For example teachers and the university had to think of new ways to offer education, but had all but time. Teachers also had to adapt to unfamiliar software to be able to continue to give lectures and keep the program and its courses going.

Figure 4 – Activity Diagram Course pre-Covid

Figure 5 – Activity Diagram Courses post-Covid

Cyber Security

Many organisations, including the education sector, have been forced to adopt new ways of remote working using new digital systems for communication and to completely rethink their business models to adapt to the realities of the COVID-19 environment (Carroll & Conboy, 2020). The digital transformation of the student journey, from registration until examination, has significantly affected the security of the sector. The process of teaching and learning at a university has been perfected over the years. The education sector is a sector where innovation is low (Tierney, Lanford, 2016) and standardization is high (Mari Elken, 2017). Logically, since diplomas must be given uniformly to students who have proven to be able to perform on the same level. Therefore, innovation requires a procedural path to ensure the quality of education and to ensure the quality of the diplomas that are given out to students.

The COVID-19 virus has disrupted the method of teaching and learning at a University. Teaching and learning whilst keeping 1.5-meter distance from others simply are not possible in a University where education is given to thousands of students. In order to be able to continue their services, the University of Tilburg had to adapt to online education to ensure the possibility of graduation for their students. Adaptation to online education entails online course registration, online lectures, online evaluation, online teamwork, online meetings, online examination and much more. Being able to do so online shifts the risk profile of the sector of education, since standardization was not possible due to the timely manner in which the transformation had to take place. So instead of taking months, maybe even years, for adapting change, the digital transformation had to take place in a matter of weeks. And this transformation has been enabled by the rapid diffusion of Information Systems (IS) technology and cloud-based infrastructure that has allowed people to maintain interaction, whilst adhering to the new norms of social distance and self-isolation (Kodama, 2020).

A digital transformation imposes several challenges and risks which are often quite complex. A University is a bureaucratic organization, meaning that its adaptability is low. Therefore, a process of digital transformation at a University is a process which takes years instead of months. The severity of the risks that come along with the digital transformation and the digital age has been highlighted by a case example of Maastricht University (Riccardo Colombo, 2020). Maastricht University was hit by a cyber-attack in October 2019. The attack started with two phishing emails that were opened by employees of Maastricht University. The phishing emails allowed the hackers to be able to compromise the systems of

the University, allowing them to hold the systems hostage until the University paid a ransom sum.

This case example underlines the importance of cyber security since the University was not able to provide education, was not aware of the impact and they did not know if the cyber hackers would keep their word after paying the ransom. The impact of the hack however, was enormous since it impacted employees, (international) students, and the quality of education which caused an increase in the costs of the University as well as the parties involved.

During the COVID19 crisis, cyberthreats have also grown at a phenomenal rate as personal data continues to be a lucrative target for hackers (K. Dwivedi, L.Hughes, C.Coombs, et al, 2020).

In order to assess the risk that the digital transformation brings to the sector, a risk impact assessment will be carried out. This assessment will provide insight into the risks which need mitigation for safekeeping of future processes. The assessment is qualitative, based on subjective judgement of scenarios. The identified risks are as follows:

- Duplication and copyright infringement (confidentiality risk) of the course materials of the professors; Professors post the materials for their courses on an application/platform accessible for the students following their courses. In this way students can access the learning material at home to study or to make assignments. It is easy for students to download papers only accessible for students of the University or make a screenshot or screen recording during the lecture.
- Leakage of personal data (confidentiality risk) of the students through a potential cyber-attack; the network of the University holds a massive amount of data about thousands of people. This data could be valuable to potential hackers who are looking to sell it or stop the operations of the University for ransom. Slow-adapting organizations are more vulnerable for attacks since they adapt their security as fast as for example agile organizations. Cyber-attacks can lead to a leak of data. Once the cyber criminals enter the network, they will be able to steal, adjust or intercept the data flow. In the case of Maastricht University, they can even hold the data captive and stop the operations of the University for ransom.
- The spread of data (integrity risk) over different (third party) applications causing a higher risk of data loss; organizations outsource many functions of their operations which lead to data of students being spread across many different applications. In the case of Tilburg University, think about Canvas, Osiris, BlackBoard, Google, Testvision et cetera. A security weakness of one of the partners of the University could lead to a data leak of personal information of students at the University.
- The possibility of fraud (integrity risk) during online examination. Online examination has no direct physical supervision, allowing for students to be able to come up with loopholes in the examination of the University in order to be able to commit fraud (Harmon, Lambrinos and Buffolino, 2010). Furthermore, online examination entails the use of applications and software, all which is vulnerable to cyber-attacks in essence.
- Breach of GDPR rights (confidentiality / compliance risk) of students to insure their education. A breach of GDPR rights is directly related to online examination, since personal data needs to be collected in abundance in order to be able to supervise students and to prevent fraud. Measures that need to be taken are digital analysis of the environment of the student (their own home), tracking of eye movement (personal biometric data) and an analysis of the computer usage and what is happening (their own computer). Furthermore, this data is collected and stored in remote servers, without students knowing where and who is able to access this data. However, the collection of personal data is needed in order to prevent any delays in the study of the students, who have to provide consent to the collection of their data.
- Denial of service attack (availability risk) means that a student cannot access information systems and softwares. Denial of Service (DoS) attacks happen by flooding the targets and sending information that causes a crash. In this case, DoS attacks on Canvas or Osiris could cost universities both time and money to fix this issue, as the attackers often ask for a ransom. Eventually, students are deprived of the educational tools they are used to study with.

Risks	Likelihood (1-5)	Impact (1-5)	Combined Risk (<10)
Duplication and copyright infringement of the course materials of the professors (confidentiality)	5	2	10
Leakage of personal data of the students through a potential cyber attack (confidentiality)	3	4	12
The spread of data over different (third party) applications causing a higher risk of data loss (Integrity)	3	4	12
The risk of cheating during an exam (Integrity)	2	5	10
Breach of GDPR rights of students to insure their education (confidentiality)	4	3	12
Denial of service through ransomware: Will make collaborative platforms for students inaccessible (availability)	2	4	8

Figure 6 – qualitative risk assessment before mitigation

The qualitative assessment of the risk as shown above shows risks at an unacceptable level (risk appetite = 10), indicated by the red and orange colors. Only the risk of a denial of service attack has a lower combined risk than the appetite risk (see green box). Further elaboration per outcome of the risk and the assessment of the risk is as follows. Examples of risk mitigation measures are also included in order to decrease the combined risk to an acceptable level.

1. Duplication and copyright infringement of the course materials of the professors

Online lectures raise the possibility of students being able to copy and distribute the contents of the course. Course content is available online so that students can access all the materials from their own workplace. Therefore, this risk contains a very high likelihood of students copying the materials since the opportunity to do so contains very little to no threshold. The impact however is considered to be significantly less since the course materials on themselves are useless to others in the sense that they don't provide others with a diploma. Furthermore, copying and distributing the materials is illegal since this is considered as copyright infringement, further lowering the impact since offenders will be prosecuted.

In order to lower the risk appetite, universities could design control measures which enable the prevention, detection or correction of a control risk. Universities could digitally stamp each file downloaded by students with an invisible tracer. This tracer contains a unique ID unreadable and inaccessible by everyone except universities themselves. Furthermore, in the case of copyright infringement, universities are able to link it back to the unique tracer, which links back to the person who actually downloaded the file with permission. Stronger persecution of copyright infringement should lead to a lower likelihood which leads to an overall lower risk. This refers to detective measures as it ensures that no risk goes unnoticed.

2. Leakage of personal data of the students through a potential cyber-attack

The likelihood of leakage of data through a potential cyber-attack is considered to be of a medium level, since the possibility of a cyber-attack is, most likely, dependent on a user error. Take the case of the Maastricht University hack; the cyber-attack was made possible due to phishing mails being opened by the users. The impact however, is enormous since the attack would harm the reputation of the University. Personal data could be leaked which leads to confidential information being available for purchase on the dark web.

The likelihood of cyber-attacks should be lowered by introducing and maintaining an up-to-date cyber security line of defense. Furthermore, personnel and students should be trained in order to detect phishing mails and potential malware downloaded to the system. This refers to preventive measures as it makes a risk nearly impossible to occur.

3. The spread of data over different (third party) applications causing a higher risk of data loss

The spread of data across multiple platforms and applications decreases the line of sight of the University as to what is being done with their data and by whom. This decrease in line of sight is not only damaging for the users within universities, who lack control of their own data and who is able to access it, but it also decreases the protection of the data against potential cyber-attacks since universities are not able to oversee the potential security risks of all their third party vendors whom the users have to use. However, the partners of the universities have to comply with certain standards before being able to process data for them. Therefore, the likelihood is considered to be medium. The impact is the same as described for risk 2; a big impact due to the size of the potential data leak.

In order to mitigate the risk of losing data by an external vendor, universities should standardize and vertically integrate their services in order to be able to protect their own data without relying on external vendors. Once again, this reflects a preventive measure as it should make a risk nearly impossible to occur.

4. The risk of cheating during an exam

All students are assumed to behave ethically following the guidelines of the University. Committing fraud in order to pass your exam is in contrary to behaving ethically. However, the digital

transformation includes online examination which raises the possibility of cheating since the technology is rather new and because a loophole can always be found in a digital environment with no physical supervision. However, the likelihood of committing fraud is considered to be low since the penalty of getting caught is a burden for a lifetime. The benefits of cheating do not outweigh the risk of getting caught. Therefore, the likelihood is considered to be relatively low. The impact of (successfully) cheating however is considered to be very high because, if done in larger quantities, this would mean that diplomas lose their value.

The likelihood of committing fraud during online examination should be further lowered in order to decrease the risk appetite. The risk should be mitigated by introducing further security measures which should actively lower the possibility of cheating. Here, corrective measures apply, as when fraud is detected, universities react appropriately (f.e. sanctions).

5. Breach of GDPR rights of students to insure their education

In order to be able to conduct business as usual after the transformation, online examination should be considered a regular aspect of the service offered by the University. However, online examination requires digital supervision; something that inevitably breaches GDPR rights of students since they are required to deliver personal data so that cheating can be detected. Eye movement, room scanning and computer monitoring are examples of how the private space of students is affected by online examination. The likelihood of breaching is therefore quite high. The impact is a point of discussion, some students do not mind, whereas others strongly disagree with the invasion of privacy.

The likelihood of breaching GDPR rights of students should be further lowered by introducing preventive measures that actively protect the rights of students. Storage of data, transfer of data and the parties involved with processing of the data should be made publicly available for the parties involved to increase transparency. Furthermore, data should be anonymized and should not be stored longer than necessary. Once again, this reflects a preventive measure as it should make a risk nearly impossible to occur.

6. Denial of service through ransomware

A denial of service through ransom software would have a huge impact on the university. Moreover, the likelihood of this happening could rise in the future due to the sudden increase in the importance

of the various software needed for the university to function properly. This is why it is important to know mitigation methods in order to be able to reduce the combined risk, even though it is already lower than the appetite risk.

The aim would therefore be to reduce it through preventive processes. This could be done by the network trafficking monitoring. This can be done by implementing firewalls and an intrusion detection system, which is a software that detects malicious activity on the system.

Risks	Likelihood (1-5)	Impact (1-5)	Combined Risk(<10)
Duplication and copyright infringement of the course materials of the professors	3	2	6
Leakage of personal data of the students through a potential cyber attack	2	4	8
The spread of data over different (third party) applications causing a higher risk of data loss	2	4	8
The risk of cheating during an exam	1	5	5
Breach of GDPR rights of students to insure their education	2	3	6
Denial of service through ransomware: Will make collaborative platforms for students inaccessible (availability)	2	3	6

Figure 7 – qualitative risk assessment after mitigation

Mitigation measures should be taken into account in order to lower the combined risk of the parties involved. Proactive security measures and an up-to-date security system with a cyber security team should be the standard for the educational sector after the digital transformation. Standardization and anonymity should be key drivers of the method of processing data by external vendors.

DISCUSSION

Covid-19 has drastically changed the digital transformation of educational institutions and required fast decision making and implementation. In these harsh times, the key objective of universities is to ensure that the quality of education stays the same or gets even better than before. In order to achieve this, it is essential to understand and cope with the challenges of online education and how to improve the processes within it.

With regard to the ITG, it can be said that before Covid-19, it followed a Business Monarchy archetype, in which IT related decisions were centralized and made by senior executives and university board members. Furthermore, the level of adoption of IT governance mechanisms was low (Yanosky and Caruso 2008). In contrast, during Covid-19, the dynamic of the educational ITG drastically changed as Business and IT representatives were now in charge of determining which IT applications should be used to ensure that universities could provide the best possible

education. This change resulted in fast decision making and offered adequate technological solutions for pursuing online education.

The integrated business process of a course has changed. This is explained by the fact that the roles of the actors within have muted. When looking at the activity diagram, we can conclude that this post-Covid-19 is way more complex than the pre-Covid-19 one. This difference is the result of the more prominent role of digital systems. However, this predominance of the digital system related activities can create a sense of incapability and frustration by the student, who is not familiar with all technical features and requirements of online education. Therefore, it is utmost important to guide the students in the online education process and ensure that the processes are made as simple as possible. Consequently, the simplicity and efficiency of the integrated “business” processes will make online education easier to follow and increase students’ satisfaction (Benson & Simpson, 2013).

During the COVID19 crisis, cybersecurity systems and processes within universities were seriously challenged and were crucial for continuing education overall. This is in line with the findings that cyberthreats have also grown at a phenomenal rate as personal data continues to be a lucrative target for hackers (K. Dwivedi, L.Hughes, C.Coombs, et al, 2020). In this particular case, five major risks have been identified as high or even critical, and should require more attention. Duplication and copyright infringement, leakage of personal data of the student through a potential cyber attack, the spread of data over different (third party) applications causing a higher risk of data loss, the risk of cheating during an exam and reach of GDPR rights of students to insure their education. Three out of six risks had a level of combined risk that was too high and required some incentives to diminish it. However, after having implemented several incentives, which were all control measures, it was concluded that risks totaled a combined risk that was below the acceptable level required by universities. It can be concluded that universities proved that they were capable of quick decision making and applying the right tools to protect the security of its systems and students.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we examined the pre-COVID-19 situation as well as the post-COVID-19 situation of IT related MSc programs at global universities in order to analyze whether quality of the education can be as good as, or even better as, offline education. The Covid-19 crisis had a profound impact on the digital transformation process of

universities.

After comparing pre Covid-19 era and the post-Covid era, we found several interesting results that could be beneficial for the future of IT MSc programs online learning. First of all, the dynamic of the educational ITG drastically changed as Business and IT representatives were now in charge of determining which IT applications should be used to ensure that universities could provide the best possible education. Despite the complexity of the new integrated business processes, IT executives should focus on making the new processes as simple as possible in order to make online education easier to follow and increase students’ satisfaction. Therefore, in further studies, the relationship between the IT governance and the processes implemented should be investigated in order to analyze which factors could scale up and optimize online education.

Furthermore, universities faced many challenges in order to make online education of IT MSc programs possible. Universities applied risk assessments and were capable of quick decision making and applying the right tools to protect the security of its systems and students. Despite these positive aspects, there are still some limitations to this study. First of all, we were not able to gather data from the online survey, due to time restrictions. Furthermore, all of the findings are based on a small amount of data and assumptions. Therefore, in future studies, the relation between online IT MSc programs and final results (GPA) of the students should be analyzed. This could give a clear illustration of whether online education is more successful than offline education.

To conclude, despite the short time frame and the limited amount of knowledge we have about Covid-19, all of these factors have led to the successful transition from offline to online education and could be applicable in the near future.

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